

SPECIATION MEASUREMENTS OF BUTYLTINS: APPLICATION TO CONTROLLED RELEASE
RATE DETERMINATION AND PRODUCTION OF REFERENCE STANDARDS

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ABSTRACT

This paper describes methods and results of the determination of release rates for organotin species released from organotin impregnated wood pilings. The analytical method consists of simultaneous extraction/hybridization of aqueous leachate samples, with organotin speciation by gas chromatography coupled with tin selective flame photometric detection (GC-FPD). The sensitivity of the FPD detector to the butyltin family of organotins is 0.1 to 0.2 ng, depending on the species. Chromatographic separation of the butyltins provides speciation of mono- through tetrabutyltin within a 15 min chromatogram, with the additional capability of identifying any methylbutyltin compounds that may be present in the sample. Water samples were collected from the piling leaching tanks immediately upon immersion of the pilings and continued to be collected for approximately 1 year. Speciation and release rate data were obtained on both the early, first order stage of organotin release, and the latter, zeroth order phase of controlled release. Instrument calibrations were performed using a specially prepared organotin research material.

INTRODUCTION

Production of organotin compounds has increased significantly during the past 30 years, to a current worldwide level of more than 35,000 tons annually¹. Numerous applications as catalysts, polymer stabilizers, and tailored biocides have resulted from the highly varied chemical and biological properties provided by different classes of organotin(IV) compounds²⁻⁷. As the use of organotins has increased, international concern for the fate and effect of these compounds in the environment has also increased. These concerns are reflected in environmental assessments and pollution evaluations compiled by industry⁸ and national environmental agencies of several countries⁹⁻¹¹.

To effectively evaluate the environmental risks associated with organotin usage, analytical methods capable of detection and speciation of butyltin compounds at concentrations in the μg to ng per liter range must be employed. For example, aquated tributyltin ion is toxic to some sensitive aquatic organisms at $\mu\text{g}/\text{l}$ levels¹², but the

dibutyltin ion is comparatively nontoxic¹³. It is essential that monitoring methods provide chemical speciation data for all the organotins present in an environmental sample in order to provide a rational, equitable and effective basis for regulation.

Within the past several years many new measurement methods have been described which provide the required ultratrace sensitivity and speciation information for organotin compounds¹⁴⁻²⁴. In general, most of these methods rely on solvent extraction of the organotins from the environmental sample, concentration and often derivitization by sodium borohydride or Grignard reagents, and subsequent chromatographic or boiling point separation with tin determination by a tin-selective (flame photometric) or tin-specific (atomic absorption) detector.

Recent research in our laboratory has been directed to the development of sensitive butyltin speciation methods²⁵ and generation of stable, aqueous solutions of tributyltin standards for use in calibrations and method intercomparisons²⁶. The measurement method relies on a simultaneous hybridization/extraction step to remove and concentrate butyltin compounds from water samples. Identification and quantitation of the butyltin species present in the sample is accomplished by injecting small aliquots of the organic extract into a gas chromatograph equipped with a flame photometric detector (GC/FPD). Butyltins ($\text{Bu}_n\text{SnX}_{4-n}$, $n = 1$ to 4) and mixed methylbutyltin species are detected at μg per liter concentrations. Variations in salinity (fresh water to seawater) and pH (6.3 to 9.4) have no effect on butyltin detection with this method. The reproducibility of the method is $\pm 10\%$ and extraction efficiency for tributyltin is close to 100%.

The preparation and distribution of a dilute (ca. 1 mg/l), aqueous, solution of tributyltin for use in an organotin measurement methods intercomparison has been described thoroughly in an NBS interagency report²⁶ and will not be described in detail here. However, the method used for monitoring the concentration and purity of the tributyltin research solution was identical to the method described in this paper.

As noted above, organotin compounds, specifically tributyltin species, are being used as the biocidal components in marine antifouling coatings. Advanced coating formulations contain tributyltin bound to carboxyl groups in a high molecular weight copolymer of tributyltin methacrylate and methylmethacrylate. Applied to ships hulls, the butyltin copolymer coatings have demonstrated years of fouling free performance²⁷. The longevity of the coating is attributed to the controlled release, at near zeroth order, of tributyltin toxicant from the copolymer matrix. Tributyltin copolymers are also being investigated for use as preservatives for the protection of wood pilings. Pilings are impregnated with a solution containing the respective monomers, which undergo reactions including polymerization in situ²⁸.

The primary goal of the piling release rate experiment was to determine the identity of the butyltin species released from the pilings and the rates of their release into artificial seawater. The experiment was designed to continue for approximately 1 year, during which time the release rate was expected to drop from a relatively high initial rate to a low, near zeroth order rate.

EXPERIMENTAL

Two types of wood pilings, both made from debarked southern yellow pine but impregnated with different tributyltin copolymer formulations, were provided by the Naval Civil Engineering Laboratory, Port Hueneme, CA 93043. The copolymers were formed in situ from reaction of tributyltin methacrylate (TBTM) and either methylmethacrylate (MMA) or glycidyl methacrylate (GMA). The pilings, 11 to 12 cm in diameter, were cut with a hand saw into small sections (22 to 24 cm long) for use as test specimens. The ends of the test specimens were sealed with epoxy glue so that the cylindrical surface of the piling would be the only site of butyltin release. Pyrex glass jars were used as containers for artificial seawater and piling specimens. Prior to use, the jars were cleaned, first by washing with a warm water and soap solution, then by leaching for two to three days with dilute (10%) aqueous nitric acid at ca. 20 °C. Following acid leaching, the jars were rinsed 4 to 5 times with deionized water. The jars were then filled with 32 liters of artificial seawater, prepared by adding salts in the following amounts (grams per liter) to deionized water; NaCl, 23.9 g; MgCl₂·6H₂O, 10.8 g; Na₂SO₄, 4.0 g; CaCl₂, 1.15 g; KCl, 0.7 g. All salts used in preparation of the artificial seawater were of reagent grade. No butyltin contaminants were detected in the artificial seawater.

To prevent the concentration of butyltins in the jars from reaching levels that might inhibit further release from the piling specimens, water was pumped continuously from the jars and passed through traps containing activated charcoal. Monitoring of butyltin concentration in the water returning to the tanks from the activated charcoal

traps showed that the traps were removing all butyltins and returning butyltin-free water to the jars. A peristaltic pump with adjustable flow rate was used to pump just enough water through the charcoal traps to keep the butyltin concentration in the jars at a low but measurable concentration, typically 5 to 15 µg per liter. The water in the jars was circulated and mixed constantly by the action of the peristaltic pump and Teflon-covered stirring bars rotating at approximately 650 rpm at the bottoms of the jars.

The piling specimens were completely submerged in the artificial seawater to initiate the release rate determination experiment. For approximately the first 48 hours of the experiment, the pumping system for organotin removal was not operated so that the initial release of butyltins could be determined. Water samples of approximately 100 ml volume were taken from the jars containing the piling test specimens and from the water returning to the jars from the charcoal traps. Samples that could not be analyzed immediately after collection were stored on crushed ice at 0°C until they were analyzed. The following procedure was used for a 100 ml sample with a butyltin concentration in the low µg per liter range. The sample was put into a 125-ml glass separatory funnel equipped with a Teflon stopcock and Teflon-lined screw cap. A spike from an aqueous solution of di-n-propyltin dichloride was added to all samples as an internal standard at a concentration of 5 or 10 ng per liter. Following addition of 2.8 ml of dichloromethane and 2.0 ml of aqueous (4% w/v) sodium borohydride, the funnel was capped and manually shaken for 1 minute. The funnel was then vented and placed on a wrist action shaker for 10 minutes. After shaking, five minutes was allowed for phase separation. The organic layer at the bottom of the funnel was then removed and placed in a 1.5-ml polypropylene centrifuge tube, and a gentle stream of compressed air was directed over the tube. An additional 1.4 ml of dichloromethane was added to the funnel and the extraction repeated. The organic layers were combined and evaporation continued until 1 ml of solution remained. Five microliters of this concentrated extract was then injected into the GC/FPD for identification and quantitation of the butyltin species present in the sample. Appropriate blanks were carried through the entire procedure.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The concentration and distribution of butyltin species present in the water surrounding the wood pilings and in the water returning to the piling tanks from the charcoal traps was periodically determined by the simultaneous extraction/hydridization method described above. Water samples were taken frequently at the beginning of the experiment (10 samples in the first 48 hours), with the sampling interval increasing as the experiment continued.

For approximately the first month that the pilings were exposed to the artificial seawater, mono-, di-, and tributyltin species were detected in the water surrounding the pilings. Both di- and tributyltin species were detected throughout the course of the experiment. Although the measurement method was capable of speciating tetrabutyltin, none was ever detected during the course of this experiment. No butyltins were ever detected in the water returning to the piling tanks from the charcoal traps either, indicating that the traps were 100% efficient in removing butyltins from the artificial seawater. The data obtained on the concentration of butyltins in the artificial seawater surrounding the pilings was converted to release rate data by use of the following equation.

$$\text{release rate} = (T_c - E_c) \times (F) \times (1440) / A$$

- T_c = Concentration of butyltin species in tank (µg/L).
- E_c = Concentration of butyltin species in water returning to tank from charcoal traps (µg/L).
- F = Flow rate of water through charcoal traps (L/min).
- 1440 = Conversion factor for calculating volume of water passing through charcoal traps per day.
- A = Square centimeter area of piling releasing organotins.

Graphs showing the release rates of tributyltin for both the TBTM/MMA and TBTM/GMA copolymer treated pilings are shown in Figures 1, 2, and 3. Release rates for mono-, di-, and tributyltin species, determined at various times during the course of the experiment for the two copolymer formulations, are listed in Tables 1 and 2.

Figure 1. Graph of tributyltin release rates for both piling copolymer formulations during the first 60 hours of piling exposure to artificial seawater.

Figure 1 shows tributyltin release rates for both copolymer formulations for approximately the first 60 hours of piling exposure to artificial seawater. The release rates reached a maximum after approximately 30 hours, then declined. The drop in the release rates is attributed to inhibition produced by the relatively high butyltin concentrations (400 to 600 µg/L) that were reached before the charcoal trap system was put into operation. Figures 2 and 3 show tributyltin release rates from day 9 to day 400 for TBTM/MMA and TBTM/GMA formulations respectively. After an exposure period of 30 to 50 days, the release rates for both copolymers had reached relatively stable rates of less than 0.5 µg per square centimeter per day.

Figure 2. Graph of the release rates for tributyltin from piling treated with copolymer TBTM/MMA. Data are plotted for day 9 through day 400 of piling immersion in artificial seawater.

Figure 3. Graph of the release rates for tributyltin from piling treated with copolymer TBTM/GMA. Data are plotted for day 9 through day 400 of piling immersion in artificial seawater.

REFERENCES

TABLE 1

Release rates of butyltins from TBTM/MMA copolymer treated piling

Immersion Time	Release Rates ($\mu\text{g}/\text{cm}^2/\text{day}$)		
	BuSn ⁺⁺⁺	Bu ₂ Sn ⁺⁺	Bu ₃ Sn ⁺
1 hr	0.6	1.15	2.02
12 hr	0.8	4.77	13.00
1.3 days	1.2	13.86	51.18
9 "	ND	1.21	3.56
20 "	0.05	0.27	0.60
43 "	ND	0.44	0.38
86 "	ND	0.34	0.45
100 "	ND	0.17	0.47
233 "	ND	0.07	0.14
400 "	ND	0.08	0.23

ND = not detected

TABLE 2

Release rates of butyltins from TBTM/MMA copolymer treated piling

Immersion Time	Release Rates ($\mu\text{g}/\text{cm}^2/\text{day}$)		
	BuSn ⁺⁺⁺	Bu ₂ Sn ⁺⁺	Bu ₃ Sn ⁺
1 hr	1.00	1.57	1.81
12 hr	2.64	9.41	16.86
1.3 days	4.70	32.00	76.72
9 "	0.11	0.36	2.83
20 "	0.17	0.17	0.44
43 "	ND	0.33	0.44
86 "	ND	0.32	0.26
100 "	ND	0.09	0.16
233 "	ND	0.06	0.16
400 "	ND	0.05	0.11

ND = not detected

CONCLUSIONS

The method described here has proven to be highly sensitive for molecular speciation of butyltin compounds in aqueous solution. The sodium borohydride derivitization step is mild enough that it induces no molecular rearrangements in the samples and works equally well with fresh water or saline samples containing butyltins at environmental concentration levels of $\mu\text{g}/\text{l}$.

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